

Bending Characteristics of Boron-Aluminium Composites

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ABSTRACT

A boron fibre reinforced aluminum composite can be expected as a material for a light weight leaf spring. In the case of composite materials, the bending characteristic depends on the configuration of the reinforcement. Composites with various configurations of boron fibres in aluminum matrix were fabricated and their bending characteristics were examined. One of the composites, in which fibres of 17 vol% were mainly distributed at directly under the surface, showed a very high bending strength. The ratio of the bending strength to the tensile strength of the composite was about 2.7 which was much higher than 1.5 for conventional spring metals or alloys.

The composites showed also high fatigue strength. The fatigue behaviour of a composite with 17 vol% of B-fibres was similar to SK 5 which was one of popular spring materials. In the case of the composite with 50 vol% of B-fibres, the fatigue behaviour was similar to SUS 420J2 which was the most excellent spring material. From these results, it was concluded that the B-Al composites have brilliant possibility to utilize as spring materials.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites have been considered as high potential materials in special fields such as aerospace technology and other various industrial fields where properties such as heat resistance, high strength, high modulus and light weight etc. are required in the materials. The demand for such high potential materials has been increasing after energy crisis to save energy and resources in every fields of technology. In such circumstances, metal matrix composites have become the centre of public attention. However they are not practically applied yet in so many fields because of the high cost of raw materials. Moreover reliability of them has not been established sufficiently yet to replace the conventional materials by the composites. The producing techniques, which have been developed for producing composites, are not always applicable in every shapes or sizes of composites. Researches on composites have been carried out mainly to obtain high strength and high modulus, but effects of configurations of the reinforcement in a composite are not clarified enough yet.

This work has been carried out to apply a B-Al composite to a light weight leaf spring by clarifying the bending and fatigue properties related to the

volume fraction of fibres(Vf) and their configuration of the reinforcement.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The B-Al green tape, which was provided by AVCO corp., was used as a raw material. The green tape consists of boron filaments of 140 μm in diameter and aluminum foil of 40 μm in thickness. The filaments were fixed in parallel with resin on the foil at every 200 μm in distance. The green tape was cut to pieces of 75 mm in width and 110 mm in length. After removing the fixing resin at 500°C for 1 hour, the pieces of the green tape were laminated and consolidated by hot-pressing. The hot pressing was carried out in a vacuum of 10^{-4} Torr at the temperature range between 500°C and 600°C under the pressure of 34 MPa by using a graphite die.

The configuration of the fibres in a composite were designed as follows:

The specimen, which was named as "UD", was made of 7 pieces of the green tape. The fibres of 110 mm in length were aligned unidirectionally in parallel to the longer side of the specimen, and the volume fraction of the fibres was about 50 vol%.

The specimen named as "L1" consisted of two pieces of the AVCO green tape and an aluminum plate of 0.7 mm in thickness. The green tape pieces were placed at each surface of the aluminum plate. The Vf of this specimen was about 17 vol%. Direction of the fibres in the composite was as same as the specimen "UD".

The specimen "L2" consisted of 4 pieces of the AVCO green tape and an aluminum plate of 0.3 mm in thickness. Two pieces of the green tape were placed on a surface of the aluminum plate and the other two were on the other side of the aluminum. The Vf was about 34 vol%. Fibre direction in the composite was as same as the above two kinds of specimens.

The specimen "CROSS" was made of 7 pieces of the AVCO green tape. In the composite, the fibres in the top and the bottom pieces of the green tape were parallel to the long side of the composite, and the fibre direction of every layer crossed alternately. The Vf was 50 vol%.

The thickness of all specimens was unified as about 1 mm.

The specimens for mechanical test were cut out from above composites by using a diamond saw. The test specimen size for the tensile test was 5 mm in width and 100 mm in length. The size of 10 mm in width and 100 mm in length was adopted for bending test. The specimen for fatigue test was 10 mm in width and 50 mm in length.

Tensile test and bending test were carried out by using an Instron type testing machine. Aluminum tabs were fixed at both ends of the specimen for tensile test to prevent the damage caused by the jaws. Three points bending method was used for bending test. The gauge length was 40 mm for the tensile test, and the span was 40 mm for the bending test.

An electro-magnetic vibrating type machine was used for the fatigue test. The vibrating rate for the fatigue test was 3000 cycle per minute. The vibration was carried out by sine mode. The fatigue test conducted in cantilever type. The initial bending, which corresponded to mean bending moment, was applied to the specimen, and the specimen was vibrated to give the formerly decided stress amplitude.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The B-Al pieces were preliminary consolidated to form a composite at various temperatures to know the optimum condition. The composite, which was fabricated at 600°C, showed the lowest strength, because deterioration of the

reinforcement was caused by the high temperature. On the other hand, the composite fabricated at 500°C was not adequately consolidated, because the temperature was too low to complete the bonding between the pieces. In the case of fabricating at 550°C, the specimen was consolidated sufficiently, and the deterioration was not so severe. Therefore the temperature for hot-pressing was decided at 550°C.

The fractography after tensile test is shown in Photos 1-a to -d. Fibres are located in the expected position for each specimen and no gap is observed at the interface between the fibre and the matrix. Moreover a B-fibre at the right which was placed at the normal direction to the tensile direction, fractured into halves along the fibre as shown in Photo 1-c. These results indicate that the bonding between fibres and matrix was rather strong.

Fig. 1-a and -b show the load-displacement curve for the specimens "L1" and "UD", which were obtained in bending test. Dotted lines in the figures indicate energy per event for acoustic emission in arbitrary unit. Broken lines means the events number. Strong acoustic emission was observed at the stress over 50% of bending strength. This phenomena will be related to the later fatigue strength.

The results of tensile strength(TS), bending strength(BS) of each specimen and the ratio of (BS/TS) are listed in Table 1. The tensile strength increased as increasing of the boron fibre content, although the strength of the specimen "UD" was about 20% lower than one presented by AVCO corp. The lower strength may be caused by the slight reaction at the interface, though no evidence was observed.

On the other hand, the bending strength depends not only on volume fraction of fibres but also on configuration of the reinforcements. Although the volume fraction of the reinforcements in the specimen "L1" was only one fourth of the specimen "UD", the bending strength of "L1" had a very high value as approximately one half of the strength of "UD", because the fibres were distributed just directly under the both surfaces.

As regards the ratio of (BS/TS), the specimen "UD" showed the value of 1.5 which was approximately similar to one of usual homogeneous materials, because of homogeneous distribution of fibres in the composite. On the contrary, the ratio of (BS/TS) for the specimen "L1" was as high as 2.68 because of the special configuration of the fibres. This means that such the configuration of reinforcements is effective when bending moment is applied to a mechanical part.

The fatigue test was conducted by applying repeated stress with mean moment which was different from applying alternative stress. Before the fatigue testing, proper bending stress should be determined. In the case of applying alternative stress, the bending stress σ_{wb} is shown as follows:

$$\sigma_{wb} = \frac{3 \cdot E \cdot h}{2 \cdot \ell^2} \cdot \delta \quad \dots\dots\dots 1)$$

- where E: Young's modulus
- h: thickness of the specimen (mm)
- ℓ: setting length (span) of the specimen (mm)
- δ: bending displacement given to the specimen (mm)

The Young's modulus E for each specimen were obtained by using a machine to obtain K_b value, which was a parameter for spring limit. The machine for K_b was the other kind of bending tester. Obtained Young's modulus from the bending test are listed in Table 2. All the values are in the range of 170-180 GPa. On the other hand, the Young's modulus from the rule of mixtures is about 120 GPa for the specimen "L1". The Young's modulus from the bending test is 40% higher

than one from the tensile test. Anyhow, the Young's modulus from the bending test was used here.

The bending stress σ_{ub} for repeated stress is empirically given as follows:

$$\sigma_{ub} = 1.66 \times \sigma_{wb} \dots\dots\dots 2)$$

The values for σ_{wb} were decided as around 40, 50 and 60% of the bending fracture strength. And the used fatigue testing machine can give a constant bending displacement. Therefore the setting length (span) for each specimen, l , was determined from equation 1). The mean moment for the repeated stress is $1/2 \times \sigma_{ub}$. Then the repeated stress was 0 to σ_{ub} .

As regards fatigue resistance, all specimens showed high values as shown in Fig. 2. The data in the figures were σ_{wb} which were converted from σ_{ub} , using equation 1). The specimen "UD" was not broken by cyclic bending of more than 10^7 times, when the bending stress is lower than half of bending fracture stress. This long fatigue life should be related to the former acoustic emission. Namely, the composite had very high fatigue life when the applied stress was lower than the stress which could break the reinforcements. Though the strain of the matrix by the bending was very large enough to cause fatigue of the matrix aluminium, the composite was not broken by the fatigue test until the fibres were broken. Therefore the fatigue property is governed by the reinforcements but not by matrix. A high value as 8×10^5 was also obtained even so the bending stress was high as 65% of bending strength.

The specimen "L2" showed 1.2×10^7 of cyclic numbers at 40% of bending strength. However the fatigue strength of this specimen decreased rapidly with increasing of the bending stress, and the fatigue fracture occurred by 4000 of cyclic stress by applying the stress of 65% of bending strength.

In the case of the specimen "L1", the specimen was not broken until 5.7×10^6 of cyclic stress when the stress was 50% of bending strength.

In the case of the specimen "CROSS", the cyclic numbers were scattered, and the value was small as 7×10^4 even if the repeated stress was as low as 40% of bending strength.

Fig. 2-a to -d show also the fatigue strength of some conventional spring materials. Comparing them with the experimental data, The specimen "UD" has almost the same fatigue strength as SUS 420J2 which is very excellent spring material. Even the specimen "L1", which contained very low volume fraction of reinforcements, shows same level of fatigue nature as SK 5 spring material which is a very popular spring material.

Photo 2-b and -c show the fractured specimens after the fatigue test. The specimen "L2" was completely broken into two pieces after fatigue test, and only one tip is shown here. On the other hand, in the specimen "UD", almost the boron fibres were fractured but the fibre near the neutral plane of the specimen were not broken, even after the bending stress dropped down in the load-displacement curve (Fig. 2-a).

From the stand point of saving the costly boron fibres, putting the fibre near the surface is effective to obtain high bending strength. However, from the fatigue results, the fibre placed at around the neutral plane seems to play a role of enhancing the fatigue life.

CONCLUSIONS

Composites can have a high ratio of bending strength to tensile strength comparing with conventional spring materials, in case of special configuration

of reinforcements. Composites have also shown high fatigue strength. Even a composite with very low volume fraction of reinforcements had almost same fatigue strength with SK 5. Composites have long fatigue life when the applied stress is lower than the stress which can break reinforcements. The fibres at around the neutral plane of bending does not play a role of reinforcement for tensile strength, but they are important to enhance the fatigue life.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful to Mr. T. Akutsu and Mr. S. Sato of NHK spring Co. LTD for their aid and helpful discussion on the fatigue test and analysis.

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Photo 1 Fractography after Tensile Test
 a) "UD" b) "L1" c) "CROSS" d) "L2"
 A fibre in d) was longitudinally fractured

Fig. 1 Load-Displacement Curve by Bending Test, a) "L1", b) "UD"
 Thick Line: load-displacement
 Dotted Line: acoustic emission energy
 Broken Line: events number

Table 1

Tensile Strength,
Bending Strength &
Ratio of (BS)/(TS)

SPECIMEN	TENSILE STRENGTH (MPa)	BENDING STRENGTH (MPa)	BS/TS
UD	1310	1980	1.51
L2	725	—	—
L1	333	892	2.68
CROSS	745	1330	1.79

Table 2

Young's Modulus
by Bending Test

SPECIMEN	THICKNESS (mm)	WIDTH (mm)	YOUNG'S MODULUS (GPa)
UD	1.80	10.00	180
L2	0.96	10.00	173
L1	0.96	10.00	172
CROSS	1.14	10.00	170

Photo 2 Fractography after Fatigue Test
 a) "L2", Gaps are observed at the Interface
 b) "L2", Broken into Two Pieces
 c) "UD", Not Separated

Fig. 2 Results of Fatigue Test
 a) "UD" b) "L2" c) "L1" d) "CROSS"
 Thick Line: SUS 420J2 for a)
 SK 5 for b) and c)
 SK 4 for d)
 Black Circle: this experiment